

Decompression-induced condensation of carbon dioxide: Experiments, and prediction of the supercooling limit using classical nucleation theory

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the nucleation of droplets from supercooled CO₂ and CO₂-rich gas during decompression, using classical nucleation theory (CNT). We model the supercooling limit employing highly accurate equations of state and compare the result with nucleation pressures determined from experimental data. The present analysis is relevant for the safety assessment of pipelines containing gaseous CO₂.

Three new full-bore decompression experiments with pure CO₂ were conducted, incorporating high-speed pressure sampling and multiple sensors to achieve precise characterization of the decompression wave speed as a function of pressure. Additionally, eight experiments with pure CO₂ and nine with CO₂-rich mixtures from the open literature were analysed.

The homogeneous equilibrium model (HEM) and delayed homogeneous equilibrium model (D-HEM) were used to calculate the decompression wave speed down to the choking condition. Across all experiments, predictions based on the saturation pressure (applied in the HEM) consistently overestimated the experimentally determined nucleation values. In contrast, those based on the supercooling limit (applied in D-HEM) showed a mean absolute percentage deviation of 3 %, with predictions randomly distributed around the experimental results.

1. Introduction

CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) has been identified as one of the key tools to mitigate climate change and reach the goals of the Paris agreement (IEA, 2022; Shukla et al., 2022). As CO₂ capture and storage sites are typically not located in the same area, a CO₂ transport infrastructure will be needed. The CO₂ can be transported in several ways. However, for large CO₂ volumes there is a consensus that pipelines will be the most cost-effective (Smith et al., 2021). Most CO₂ pipelines operating today transport the CO₂ in the dense phase, a single-phase state that, upon decompression, will approach the phase envelope from the liquid side. This is considered the most economical option (Roussanaly et al., 2013).

For practical reasons, there is also interest in transportation of CO₂ in the gas phase. This may allow for the repurposing of old pipelines that cannot sustain the high pressures for dense phase transport. Carbon Limits and DNV (2021) found no showstoppers for the repurposing of existing offshore and onshore pipelines for gaseous CO₂ transport.

Another main case for pipe transport of CO₂ in the gas phase is for onshore pipes connecting emitters to ports, where the CO₂ can be sent

to an offshore pipeline operating in the dense phase. Planned projects include the European Porthos project, where a 30 km long pipeline will be used for onshore transport of CO₂ through the Rotterdam area in the gaseous state at about 35 bar (Porthos, 2023). There are also several projects underway in China for the construction of CO₂ transmission pipelines (Bin et al., 2024). Three of these are completed, all of which will transport the CO₂ in the gas phase.

For the safety assessment of pressurized pipelines, the decompression behaviour of the fluid inside the pipe must be known. This is relevant, e.g., for assessing the design limits with respect to the development of a running ductile fracture (RDF) in the pipe (Munkejord et al., 2016). Several experimental and numerical studies have been conducted for the decompression of CO₂ and CO₂-rich mixtures in the dense phase. Examples include the studies conducted by Botros et al. (2016, 2017a,b,c), Cosham et al. (2011, 2012, 2016), Drescher et al. (2014), Log et al. (2024a), Michal et al. (2018) and Munkejord et al. (2020, 2021). During the depressurization of CO₂ towards atmospheric pressure, phase change will occur. For decompression from the dense or liquid phase, the fluid will flash, creating bubbles. The pressure at which this phase change occurs is a key parameter in RDF assessment, and the current

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state of the art is to calculate the pressure assuming full thermodynamic equilibrium (Michal et al., 2020; Skarsvåg et al., 2023).

However, it has been well established in the literature for decompression from the dense phase that the phase change often occurs delayed, at a lower pressure than expected, see, e.g., Brown et al. (2014, 2013), Log et al. (2024a,b), Michal et al. (2020), Munkejord et al. (2020) and Wilhelmsen and Aasen (2022). This is a non-equilibrium effect, and it is related to how the bubbles form. For decompression from the gas phase, the fluid will condense, forming droplets. There have been relatively few studies on CO₂ gas decompression (Cosham et al., 2011, 2012; Mahgerefteh et al., 2012). Nearly all of these studies have been conducted at the same initial pressure of 4 MPa. To the authors' knowledge, possible non-equilibrium effects for CO₂ gas decompression have not yet been studied or modelled. In order to gain insight on possible non-equilibrium effects, a more varied parameter space is needed. Therefore, three new pipe depressurization tests with different initial pressures have been conducted and are presented in this work. We further address the modelling of gas decompression with non-equilibrium condensation.

Phase transitions, such as condensation, cavitation, boiling and crystallization, often proceed through a process known as nucleation. However, in extreme cases where a gas is cooled far below its saturation temperature, phase transitions may proceed via spinodal decomposition, where density fluctuations grow spontaneously throughout the system. The rate-limiting step of nucleation involves the formation of a region of the new phase that reaches a critical size, enabling spontaneous growth of the new phase. This phenomenon forms the foundation of classical nucleation theory (CNT), a widely used framework for predicting the rates and properties of nucleating clusters (Debenedetti, 1997; Kashchiev, 2000; Vehkamäki, 2006). CNT can be used as a tool to predict phase change, by defining the large-scale phase change to occur at a critical nucleation rate of the new phase. For bubble formation, this is denoted the superheat limit. For condensation, we denote this the supercooling limit – the limit at which the gas cannot be cooled further before we observe the phase change.

While CNT provides a qualitative basis for understanding nucleation in pure fluids, it often falls short quantitatively, showing discrepancies as large as 7 orders of magnitude in predicted nucleation rates for a simple substance like argon (Wedekind et al., 2007). Similarly, CNT predictions for multicomponent nucleation rates can be off by many orders of magnitude, and unphysical in the case of binary mixtures of water and strongly interacting molecules like alkanols. Aasen et al. (2020) showed that the erroneous negative number of particles in the critical embryo predicted by CNT in systems with strongly interacting molecules could be resolved by correcting for the curvature dependence in the surface tension. The curvature dependence of surface tension, including the Tolman length and the rigidity constants from the Helfrich expansion, is not readily available but can be estimated using classical density functional theory and density gradient theory (Aasen et al., 2023). The limitations of the capillarity approximation have also been addressed through a generalization of the classical Gibbs method, providing a more accurate description of the work of cluster formation down to the spinodal (Schmelzer et al., 2000).

For a mixture of CO₂ and volatile impurities like hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, argon and methane, the binary interactions are weak, and CNT is expected to perform qualitatively well without curvature corrections, avoiding unphysical predictions like negative particle numbers in the critical embryo. The same applies to mixtures including the moderately polar sulfur dioxide molecule. At low degrees of supercooling, curvature corrections to the surface tension are expected to be small and can therefore be neglected. Although the CNT nucleation rates deviate by many orders of magnitude, the limits of superheat or supercooling are well predicted by CNT due to its exponential dependence on pressure, making it relatively insensitive to the critical nucleation rate (Debenedetti, 1997; Skarsvåg et al., 2023).

Hammer et al. (2022) developed a delayed homogeneous equilibrium model, D-HEM, for decompressing flows. D-HEM is based on flow invariants and the CNT prediction of the limit of superheat in the case of bubble nucleation. Hammer et al. (2022) applied D-HEM to predict steady-state flow in nozzles and orifices for dense-phase CO₂. Later, the D-HEM formalism was extended to describe the decompression wave of CO₂-rich mixtures initially in the dense phase (Skarsvåg et al., 2023). The D-HEM takes advantage of the fact that rapid decompression can be viewed as quasi steady from a process point of view. As a result, detailed spatial and temporal integration is not needed, and a full computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation is avoided. In the present work, the D-HEM is extended to pipe decompression of CO₂ and CO₂-rich gas mixtures by a droplet nucleation model based on CNT. However, instead of employing the CNT assumptions of ideal gas and incompressible liquid, we calculate the fluid properties using an equation of state.

The approach proposed in this work is general and can be applied to other systems with mixtures dominated by a single component, where droplets nucleate. By leveraging cross-disciplinary knowledge, we obtain valuable insights into the supercooling limit of CO₂ mixtures. Notably, our approach utilizes highly accurate equations of state to predict metastable fluid properties and introduces a model where the supercooling limit can be continuously plotted up to the critical point for fluid mixtures, offering a novel and comprehensive framework for studying nucleation phenomena.

One key impact we aim to achieve is to establish models incorporating supercooling limit predictions using CNT as a new standard for engineering and safety analysis in the assessment of ductile fracture propagation in pipelines. By advancing the understanding of nucleation phenomena and offering an accurate and simple framework for numerical predictions, we aim to contribute to more efficient pipeline design.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. In Section 2, the experiments are briefly presented. In Section 3 the D-HEM for gas decompression is described. The results are presented in Section 4. Finally, concluding remarks are provided in Section 5.

2. Experiments

In this section, an overview of existing CO₂ gas decompression tests is provided. We then present the experimental facility, experimental procedure and initial conditions of the experiments conducted in the present work.

2.1. Previous experiments from literature

An overview of previous CO₂ gas decompression experiments available in the literature is shown in Table 1. Several tests have been conducted, both for pure CO₂ and CO₂-rich mixtures. The data with the highest resolution in terms of pressure sensor distribution and high frequency measurements are available from the tests of Munkejord et al. (2020) and Botros et al. (2017a). The remaining tests generally have fewer pressure sensors with lower frequency data recordings, and often only the depressurization wave speed is reported in the publications.

2.2. The ECCSEL depressurization facility

The experiments of the present work were conducted at the ECCSEL depressurization facility. This facility has previously been employed by Log et al. (2024a,b) and Munkejord et al. (2020, 2021). See Munkejord et al. (2020) for a more detailed description. A brief overview is provided here for completeness.

The ECCSEL depressurization facility (ECCSEL, 2023) has a test section consisting of a 61.67 m pipe made of stainless steel. The inner diameter of the pipe is 40.8 mm. A rupture disk with a disk holder is installed at the pipe outlet, and the pipe is densely instrumented with pressure and

Table 1Overview of full-bore decompression tests for pure CO₂ and CO₂-rich mixtures from an initial gaseous state or high-pressure gaseous-like state.

Reference	Name	Mixture composition (mol %)	P_0 (MPa)	T_0 (°C)
Munkejord et al. (2020) [†]	Test 3	100.0 % CO ₂	4.0	10.2
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 02	100.0 % CO ₂	3.9	4.9
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 03	100.0 % CO ₂	3.9	5.1
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 04	100.0 % CO ₂	3.9	20.2
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 13	100.0 % CO ₂	3.7	10.9
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 14	100.0 % CO ₂	3.7	10.9
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 16	100.0 % CO ₂	3.9	5.0
Maxey (1983) ^{**}		100.0 % CO ₂	6.0	23.2
CO ₂ with impurities				
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 05	97.0 % CO ₂ , 3.0 % H ₂	3.9	5.1
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 06	96.0 % CO ₂ , 4.0 % N ₂	3.8	5.3
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 07	99.1 % CO ₂ , 0.9 % SO ₂	3.9	9.9
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 08	95.7 % CO ₂ , 3.3 % H ₂ , 1.0 % SO ₂	3.9	10.0
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 09	94.8 % CO ₂ , 4.2 % N ₂ , 1.0 % SO ₂	3.9	10.0
Cosham et al. (2011) [†]	Test 10	88.9 % CO ₂ , 7.9 % N ₂ , 1.1 % O ₂ , 1.1 % CH ₄ , 1.0 % SO ₂	3.9	5.1
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 11	89.4 % CO ₂ , 3.2 % H ₂ , 3.8 % N ₂ , 1.3 % O ₂ , 1.1 % CH ₄ , 1.2 % SO ₂	3.7	16.3
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 12	95.7 % CO ₂ , 3.3 % H ₂ , 1.0 % SO ₂	3.9	10.0
Botros et al. (2017a) [†]	Test #34	83.3 % CO ₂ , 3.5 % N ₂ , 5.8 % O ₂ , 7.4 % Ar	13.4	59.1

[†] High resolution, high-frequency pressure recordings.

^{**} Initial density specified to 12.2 lb ft⁻³.

[†] See also Mahgerefteh et al. (2012).

[†] See also Cosham et al. (2012).

Fig. 1. Test section (dimensions are not to scale; pipe no. 5–10 and corresponding sensors are omitted.).

temperature sensors to capture the pressure transient once the rupture disk breaks. Fig. 1 shows a schematic overview of the pipe.

In the present work, layered plastic rupture disks were applied to reach the intended initial pressure before disk rupture. During pressure build-up, the main focus was on following the desired isentropes to ensure that a sudden decompression would lead to phase change at different regions along the saturation curve.

Along the pipe, 16 fast-response pressure transducers of the type Kulite CTL-190(M) are flush-mounted to the inner surface to capture the pressure transients during depressurization. The logging frequency of the data from the pressure transducers is 100 kHz, and for previous depressurization experiments the total measurement uncertainty has been estimated to be around 60 kPa. The high-frequency data are stored from 0.3 s before disk rupture for a 9 s period. The reported initial conditions of the experiments are calculated from the data between 1 ms and 0.5 ms before disk rupture.

2.3. New experiments conducted in this work

In the present work, three new CO₂ gas depressurization experiments were conducted. The initial conditions of the tests are summarized in Table 2. The conditions were chosen to complement the previous pure

Table 2New full-bore decompression tests for pure CO₂.

Name	P_0 (MPa)	T_0 (°C)
Test 28	5.73	23.4
Test 30	6.39	36.4
Test 31	4.09	16.0

CO₂ gas decompression tests presented in Section 2.1, and to validate the nucleation predictions and the D-HEM for gas decompression tests by covering a range of relevant initial entropies. In particular, Test 28 and 30 cover initial entropies which have not been studied before, while Test 31 provides a reference for comparison with data from other sources. The initial temperature-pressure conditions of the new experiments are plotted alongside the initial conditions of previous pure CO₂ experiments in Fig. 2. The figure also illustrates where the experiments intersect the saturation curve, assuming isentropic decompression.

Fig. 2. Pure CO₂ experiments. The dots represents the initial conditions of the experiments, and the dashed curves show the isentropic path down to the saturation curve. The test numbers are provided for the initial conditions of the present work.

(a) Test 3 of Munkejord *et al.* (2020) with pure CO₂. (b) Test 10 (88.9% CO₂, 7.9% N₂, 1.1% O₂, 1.1% CH₄, 1.0% SO₂) of Cosham *et al.* (2011).

Fig. 3. Illustrations of the saturation curve together with the gas spinodal curve and the supercooling-limit (SCL) curve. The isentrope illustrates the isentropic decompression path down to the SCL curve. The initial condition of the decompression is shown as a dot.

2.4. Wave speed derived from the experimental data

The decompression wave speed is evaluated by considering the arrival time at the pressure sensors of given pressure levels from the depressurization wave, as described by Munkejord *et al.* (2020). The wave speed is found by linearly fitting the arrival times of the given pressure level at the pressure sensors as a function of their position. The pressure sensors should be located close together, to minimize the effect of friction, but enough sensors should be applied to obtain a good result despite varying sensor performance. In the present work, we chose to consider three sensors, at the positions 8 cm, 28 cm and 80 cm from the open end of the pipe. These sensors provided consistent results for the experiments, while being close enough to avoid significant effects of friction.

3. The D-HEM for gas decompression

In order to utilize the D-HEM (Hammer *et al.*, 2022) to predict the decompression behaviour of pure CO₂ and CO₂-rich gas mixtures in a pipe, we develop a theory for the supercooling limit (SCL) based on classical nucleation theory (CNT). CNT is used to describe homogeneous droplet nucleation and is combined with the flow invariants of the Euler equations for 1D fluid flow to predict the depressurization behaviour.

Before delving into the model details, we provide an overview of the thermodynamic ‘landscape’, focusing on the temperature and pressure variations during the isentropic decompression. Fig. 3a shows a pure CO₂ decompression case where fluid in an initially stable gaseous state at 4.0 MPa and 10.2 °C is isentropically cooled as the pressure drops in the pipeline. The isentrope illustrates the stable gas phase down to the saturation curve; beyond this point, it transitions into a metastable gaseous state until reaching the supercooling limit. The figure also includes the gas spinodal calculated from the equation of state (EOS), see Aursand *et al.* (2017) for details. Fig. 3b shows the corresponding isentropic path for a CO₂-rich mixture initially at 3.9 MPa and 5.1 °C. This overview highlights the thermodynamic behaviour of CO₂ and CO₂-rich mixtures during decompression, illustrating the transitions from stable to metastable states along the isentropic path in temperature-pressure space. The figures also demonstrate the positioning of the supercooling limit and the gas spinodal relative to the saturation line.

3.1. Decompression wave speed

The decompression wave speed, $c - u$, is determined by the speed of sound of the rarefaction wave, c , relative to the flow velocity, u . This speed is found from the eigenvalues of the Euler equations, assuming

one-dimensional flow. Under the isentropic conditions of the Euler equations, the result can be expressed as

$$c(P) - |u(P)| = c(P) - \int_P^{P_{\text{init}}} \frac{dP'}{\rho(P')c(P')}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the mixed phase fluid density and P_{init} is the initial pressure. In the case of single-phase flow, the properties in Eq. (1) are straightforward to calculate from an EOS. However, for two-phase flow, the situation becomes more complicated. In this case, the speed of sound calculated for the two-phase mixture depends on the assumptions made in the flow model. The decompression wave speed from the initial state in a pipe to the choking flow condition is applied in engineering methods to assess design criteria to avoid running ductile fracture in pipes (Michal *et al.*, 2020; Skarsvåg *et al.*, 2023). The current state of the art in these models is to apply the homogeneous equilibrium model in calculating the decompression speed in a two-phase state.

In the derivation of the above expression for the homogeneous equilibrium flow model (HEM), full mechanical and thermodynamic equilibrium is assumed, i.e., for a two-phase state, the phases have the same velocity, pressure, temperature and chemical potential. These assumptions lead to a discontinuous speed of sound at the phase boundary, see Hammer *et al.* (2022), and further, to a jump in the decompression-wave speed as a function of pressure. Hammer *et al.* (2022) introduced the delayed homogeneous equilibrium model, D-HEM, which accounts for a possible delay in the phase change. In the case of the D-HEM for gas decompression, the jump in decompression-wave speed is shifted from the saturation state to the supercooling limit. As an example, Fig. 4 shows calculated decompression wave speeds, employing both HEM and D-HEM, for the experiments of Fig. 3. The discontinuity in the speed of sound when droplets form appears as an isobaric plateau in the figure. The experiments are not expected to display true discontinuities, but nevertheless to show clear change in the decompression wave speed allowing for the identification of droplet nucleation. In the figure, the decompression curve is plotted down to $c - u = 0$, known as the choking condition.

3.2. Droplet nucleation model

In order to estimate the liquid supercooling limit, we seek to establish a droplet nucleation model. Condensation is an activated process occurring via the formation of a droplet that reaches a critical size within a supercooled gas. In the framework of CNT, the nucleation rate is expressed as an Arrhenius equation (Aasen *et al.*, 2023; Vehkamäki, 2006),

$$J = J_0 \exp\left(\frac{-W_*}{k_B T}\right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4. Decompression wave speed curve calculated from Eq. (1).

where W_* is the work associated with the formation of critically sized droplet, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature. The prefactor is given by

$$J_0 = \beta_* C Z, \quad (3)$$

where β_* is the condensation coefficient, C is the normalization factor of the cluster size distribution and, Z , is the Zeldovich factor. The equations defining β_* , C , and Z will be provided later in this section.

In CNT, simplifying assumptions of ideal gas and incompressible liquid are typically applied, but the fluid phases can easily be described using an EOS. With a suitable Helmholtz-free-energy-based EOS, the chemical potentials of the phases (μ) and the pressure (P) will be consistently described from thermodynamic differentials given the temperature and molecular densities (ρ). In the following, the gas and liquid phase are denoted using the subscripts g and ℓ , respectively. In addition, bold symbols are used to represent vector quantities.

The nucleation rate is calculated for states where the bulk gas and the droplet are in chemical equilibrium. This equilibrium criterion is defined by the following equation,

$$\mu(T, \rho_g) = \mu(T, \rho_\ell). \quad (4)$$

Given the molecular density of the gas, ρ_g , the droplet molecular density, ρ_ℓ , can be calculated. The pressure of the phases are calculated from the EOS by

$$P_k = P(T, \rho_k), \quad k \in g, \ell. \quad (5)$$

For a perfectly spherical droplet, the work of formation for the critical droplet is Kashchiev (2000) and Vehkamäki (2006),

$$W_* = \frac{4\pi}{3} \sigma r_*^2, \quad (6)$$

where σ denotes the surface tension of the droplet. The droplet radius is under the capillary approximation calculated from the Laplace equation as Aasen *et al.* (2020) and Kashchiev (2000)

$$r_* = \frac{2\sigma}{P_\ell - P_g}. \quad (7)$$

The condensation coefficient (β_*) represents the likelihood that a cluster will grow upon collision with a monomer (gas molecule). In typical gases, monomers are far more numerous than clusters, making monomer-cluster collisions much more frequent than cluster-cluster collisions, which can thus be neglected. It is also assumed that clusters lose mass only through the detachment of single monomers. Note that we are here considering a multicomponent mixture. The probability of successful adhesion to a cluster depends on both the concentration of monomers of component i , and the monomer-cluster collision frequency

($\bar{\beta}_{*,i}$) (Vehkamäki, 2006),

$$\beta_{*,i} = \frac{1}{v_{g,i}^-} \bar{\beta}_{*,i}, \quad (8)$$

where we follow the common practice of using the ideal gas assumption, $v_{g,i}^- = y_i P_g / k_B T$, when calculating the concentration of monomers of component i . Here, y_i is the mole fraction of component i in the gas phase.

According to kinetic gas theory, the collision frequency of type i monomers with clusters ($*$) is given by Friedlander (2000) as

$$\bar{\beta}_{*,i} = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi}\right)^{1/6} \sqrt{\frac{6k_B T}{m_*} + \frac{6k_B T}{m_i} \left(V_*^{1/3} + v_{\ell,i}^{1/3}\right)^2}, \quad (9)$$

where m is the weight. The partial molar (molecular) volume of the liquid phase is calculated from the EOS using

$$v_{\ell,i} \equiv \left. \frac{\partial V_\ell}{\partial N_i} \right|_{N_j, T, P}, \quad (10)$$

where V is volume and N is the number of molecules.

As an approximation to the condensation coefficient of the mixture, we simply average the values from Eq. (8) to obtain an overall condensation coefficient of the droplet,

$$\beta^* = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_{*,i}. \quad (11)$$

For the pure fluid case, the above expression reduces to the theoretically correct value. For the cases considered in this work, the CO₂ concentration is larger than or equal to 88.9%. We therefore expect the above simplification to be reasonable. Generally, the average growth rate of a multicomponent mixture droplet is dependent on the direction of droplet growth in the size-composition plane (Ohta and Jan, 1982; Stauffer, 1976; Trinkaus and Jun, 1983; Vehkamäki and Ford, 2000), but this will not be pursued in this work.

In their work on binary nucleation, Wilemski and Wyslouzil (1995) proposed a normalization factor of the cluster size distribution, C , depending on the bulk phase molecular densities. For a pure fluid, the term reduces to the molecular density. In this work we approximate the normalization factor using the ideal-gas molecular density, motivated by the single-component expression used by Vehkamäki (2006),

$$C = \frac{P_g}{k_B T}. \quad (12)$$

The Zeldovich factor, Z , using the concept of virtual monomer volume becomes (Kulmala and Viisanen, 1991),

$$Z = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{k_B T} \frac{v_\ell}{2\pi r_*^2}}. \quad (13)$$

(a) Pressure-temperature space.

(b) Temperature-density space.

Fig. 5. Pure CO₂ saturation curve (black), the supercooling-limit curve (SCL) for the droplet nucleation (blue), the gas spinodal (dashed black) and the equilibrium properties of the critically sized droplet (orange, see Eqs. (4) and (5)) are shown. The SCL is shown for a nucleation rate of $J_{\text{crit}} = 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

For a given temperature, one must decide on a critical nucleation rate that represents the observed sudden phase change. The exact value of the critical nucleation rate (J_{crit}) has little influence on the predicted limit of superheat for bubble nucleation (Debenedetti, 1997). The same applies to the SCL for CO₂ droplets, as can be seen in the results section.

Given temperature, gas composition, y and critical nucleation rate, Eq. (2) can be solved for the gas mixture density, ρ_g ,

$$J(T, y\rho_g) = J_{\text{crit}} \quad (14)$$

to determine the SCL. Fig. 5 shows the SCL for pure CO₂ together with the saturation curve and the gas spinodal calculated from the EOS. Here, Fig. 5a provides a pressure-temperature plot including the predicted droplet pressure, while Fig. 5b gives a temperature-density plot including the predicted density of the critically-sized droplets.

3.3. Thermophysical models

The most accurate equations of state that can be applied for the modelling of CO₂ and CO₂-rich mixtures today are the EOS-CG (Gernert and Span, 2016; Neumann et al., 2023) and the GERG-2008 EOS (Kunz and Wagner, 2012). EOS-CG has been tuned specifically for mixtures of CO₂ with relevant gases produced during combustion. The GERG-2008 EOS is made for natural gas mixtures, but is also accurate for CO₂ mixtures. These multiparameter EOSs have unparalleled accuracy in the stable regions of the phase diagram. However, the presence of a second Maxwell loop renders their predictions unreliable in the metastable and unstable region (Hammer et al., 2024). The second Maxwell loop seems to be an artefact of the functional form and parameterization (Wilhelmsen et al., 2017).

Despite these deficiencies, we have chosen to use the GERG-2008 EOS in this work due to its accurate density predictions. Since the GERG-2008 EOS behaves slightly better than EOS-CG in the metastable region, it is easier to work with numerically. As the droplet nucleation state at the supercooling limit is fairly close to the saturation state, as illustrated in Fig. 5b, reasonable accuracy can be expected with the EOS. To include SO₂ with GERG-2008, we extend the model using the multiparameter model of Gao et al. (2016), and the binary interactions models of EOS-CG (Herrig, 2018; Neumann et al., 2023). The accuracy of property predictions in the metastable region of the EOS is difficult to quantify. However, given that these models are accurate to experimental precision in the stable region, they are expected to extrapolate with good accuracy into the metastable region near the saturation curve.

To estimate the surface tension of CO₂ mixtures, we employ the parachor method (Huggill and Welsenes, 1986; Sugden, 1924; Weinaug and Katz, 1943). The surface tension is then estimated as

$$\sigma_{\text{mix}} = (\mathcal{P}_\ell \rho_\ell - \mathcal{P}_g \rho_g)^m, \quad (15)$$

where \mathcal{P}_k denotes the parachor of phase k ,

$$\mathcal{P}_\ell = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \mathcal{P}_{ij}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{P}_g = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n y_i y_j \mathcal{P}_{ij} \quad (16)$$

and

$$\mathcal{P}_{ij} = (1 - \delta_{ij}) \frac{\mathcal{P}_i + \mathcal{P}_j}{2}, \quad (17)$$

where δ_{ij} is a binary interaction parameter, x_i and y_i are the molar compositions of the liquid and gas phases, respectively. m is set to 3.87, as applied in REFPROP v10 (Log et al., 2023). We use the pure fluid correlations of Mulero et al. (2012) to estimate the pure fluid parachors as a function of temperature:

$$\mathcal{P}_i = \frac{\sigma_i(T)^{1/m}}{\rho_\ell - \rho_g}. \quad (18)$$

For this work, we assume ideal mixing, i.e., the binary interaction parameter is set to zero ($\delta_{ij} = 0$). To the best of the authors' knowledge, no relevant binary experimental data are available for carbon dioxide and the other species, making us unable to correlate the most important interaction parameters.

4. Results and discussion

In this section, we present the results of our investigation into the modelling of the supercooling limit, comparing with data from decompression experiments. The first subsection examines the sensitivity of the supercooling limit to the critical nucleation rate, exploring how variations in this rate affect the overall behaviour of the system. In the second subsection, we focus on the prediction of the supercooling limit, comparing the outcomes from the CNT-based model, evaluating its accuracy in capturing experimental observations. Together, these analyses provide a deeper understanding of the role of nucleation rates and modelling approaches in determining the supercooling limit during decompression processes.

4.1. Sensitivity to the supercooling limit determined by the critical nucleation rate.

Fig. 6 shows the supercooling limit for pure CO₂ together with the saturation curve calculated from the EOS. Fig. 6a shows a pressure-temperature plot, while Fig. 6b shows a temperature-density plot. In both plots the sensitivity to the value of the critical nucleation rate is illustrated by plotting the supercooling limit for three different rates, $J_{\text{crit}} = 10^6/\text{m}^3 \text{ s}$, $J_{\text{crit}} = 10^{12}/\text{m}^3 \text{ s}$ and $J_{\text{crit}} = 10^{18}/\text{m}^3 \text{ s}$. As can be seen, the SCL is nearly insensitive to the choice of critical nucleation rate. The

(a) Pressure-temperature space.

(b) Temperature-density space.

Fig. 6. Pure CO₂ saturation curve (black), the supercooling-limit curve (SCL) for the droplet nucleation (blue) plotted for three choices of critical nucleation rates, $J_{crit} = 10^6/m^3s$ (dashed), $J_{crit} = 10^{12}/m^3s$ (solid) and $J_{crit} = 10^{18}/m^3s$ (dotted).

(a) Test 28.

(b) Test 30.

(c) Test 31.

Fig. 7. Decompression speeds of new experiments (green), compared to HEM (blue) and D-HEM (orange) calculations. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure is indicated as a red star.

insensitivity is due to the exponential behaviour of the nucleation rate. This is similar to what is observed for the critical nucleation rate when predicting the limit of superheat for bubble nucleation (Debenedetti, 1997).

4.2. Prediction of the supercooling limit

Fig. 7 illustrates the decompression speed for the experiments conducted in this campaign. The experimental decompression speeds are compared with the calculated results from the HEM and D-HEM. In the D-HEM, the pressure plateau lies below that of the HEM due to delayed droplet nucleation and the metastable path down to the supercooling

limit. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure is indicated by a red star; however, it is associated with some uncertainty as the experimental data do not exhibit a distinct plateau, but rather a change in gradient. Quantifying the uncertainty in the experimental decompression curve is challenging, as it depends on averaging data from three sensors to determine the speed of the rarefaction wave travelling in the pipe. Deriving the nucleation pressure from the decompression curve involves detecting when the gradient of pressure with respect to decompression velocity undergoes a substantial change. The nucleation pressure is then determined by the intersection of the linear curve fits for the points directly above and below the detected discontinuity in the gradient.

Table 3

Summary of decompression experiments for CO₂-rich mixtures, showing nucleation pressure, saturation pressure (sat), and the supercooling limit (SCL), with deviations from experimental values reported as percentages (%). The pure CO₂ experiments are shown at the top of the table while the CO₂-rich mixtures are shown at the bottom of the table.

Ref	Name	P_N (MPa)	P_{sat} (MPa)	ϵ_{sat} (MPa)	P_{SCL} (MPa)	ϵ_{SCL} (%)
This work	Test 28	4.64	5.09	9.84	4.70	1.46
This work	Test 30	3.80	4.39	15.6	3.88	2.12
This work	Test 31	2.31	3.01	30.3	2.39	3.36
Munkejord et al. (2020)	Test 3	2.87	3.50	21.9	2.89	0.89
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 02	3.35	3.83	14.3	3.25	-2.91
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 03	3.23	3.83	18.4	3.25	0.57
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 04	1.89	2.41	27.6	1.79	-4.90
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 13	1.99	2.79	40.2	2.17	8.90
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 14	2.19	2.79	27.7	2.17	-0.81
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 16	3.20	3.77	17.7	3.19	-0.42
Maxey (1983)		5.26	5.59	6.15	5.29	0.59
CO ₂ with impurities						
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 05	2.83	3.60	27.2	3.00	6.10
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 06	2.83	3.50	23.5	2.88	1.93
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 07	2.81	3.53	25.9	2.93	4.30
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 08	2.84	3.40	19.6	2.78	-2.08
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 09	2.57	3.37	28.0	2.74	4.02
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 10	2.72	3.56	30.8	2.91	6.86
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 11	2.71	3.66	35.0	3.01	11.0
Cosham et al. (2011)	Test 12	1.77	2.38	34.9	1.77	0.28
Botros et al. (2017a)	Test #34	7.02	7.45	6.14	7.26	3.45

* Two plateaus are observed; the lowest plateau is reported. Errors with the highest plateau value for the saturation and the supercooling limit are 7.0% and -16.9%, respectively.

Fig. 8. Saturation pressure (blue) and the supercooling-limit pressure (green) are plotted against the experimentally derived nucleation pressure for all experiments listed in Table 3. Dashed black lines indicate deviations of $\pm 20\%$, while the solid black line represents 0% deviation.

All experiments show an initial undershoot of the two-phase equilibrium decompression speed below the supercooling limit, before relaxing towards the modelled decompression speed at lower pressures. Whether this behaviour results from a physical process or is an artefact of the averaging procedure in our calculation of the wave speed remains unclear. Notably, in the case of Test 31 the experimental decompression curve follows the metastable path (D-HEM) perfectly before two-phase flow is observed. For both Test 28 and Test 30, there is a more gradual transition toward the two-phase branch. In all cases, the CO₂ gas decompression experiments show clear non-equilibrium in the transition from single to two-phase flow.

Table 3 summarizes all the available decompression experiments of CO₂-rich mixtures, presenting the nucleation pressure derived from experimental data, the saturation pressure (HEM) and the supercooling limit for isentropic decompression (D-HEM). Both models are compared to the experimental nucleation pressure, with deviations reported as percentages (%). The results show that the saturation pressure consistently overpredicts the nucleation pressure, whereas the supercooling

limit aligns closely with the experimental data. The deviations between the experimentally derived nucleation pressure and model predictions are illustrated in Fig. 8.

Plots of decompression speed for the previous experiments found in the literature are provided in A. Based on all experimentally derived nucleation pressures, the magnitude of the critical nucleation rate was adjusted to $J_{crit} = 10^{14} \text{m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$, a relatively high value. This choice yielded slightly better results compared to using smaller values. With this choice of critical nucleation rate, the mean absolute percentage deviation (MAPD) of the calculated supercooling limit compared to the experimentally derived nucleation pressure across all experiments is 3%. In comparison, the MAPD of the calculated saturation pressure compared to the experimentally derived nucleation pressure across all experiments is 23%.

The reduced agreement between the model and the CO₂-mixture experimental results raises questions about the applicability of the simple approximation for the condensation coefficient. However, multiple sources of uncertainty make it challenging to attribute the offset solely to this assumption without more detailed experiments. For mixtures, additional uncertainty arises from the predicted mixture surface tension, compounded by uncertainties in the calculation of the decompression curve, as observed for pure CO₂ as well. These uncertainties include the averaging of noise in pressure measurements and variability in initial conditions.

In Tests 04 and 14 of Cosham et al. (2011), some wobbling is observed in the experimental pressure versus decompression-speed curves, see Fig. A.2. This behaviour may result from noise in the pressure measurements, uncertainties in the calculation of decompression speed, or inhomogeneities in the pipe fluid. For Test 04, temperature inhomogeneity could be a contributing factor, while for Test 14, both temperature and compositional inhomogeneity are potential causes.

Fig. 8 illustrates the deviations between the experimentally derived nucleation pressure, the predicted saturation pressure and the supercooling-limit pressure. The saturation pressure consistently overpredicts the nucleation pressure across all cases, with the relative deviation increasing as the nucleation pressure decreases. In contrast, the deviations in the supercooling-limit pressure predictions appear to be randomly distributed.

5. Conclusion

This study employs classical nucleation theory (CNT) to describe the nucleation of droplets from supercooled CO₂ and CO₂-rich gases during decompression. Employing highly accurate equations of state and parachor-based surface tension predictions, we have determined the supercooling limit and compared it with experimentally observed nucleation pressures from CO₂ pipe decompression tests. Consistent with findings for the limit of superheat in bubble nucleation, the predicted supercooling limit was found to be relatively insensitive to variations in the critical nucleation rate.

During the decompression of a pipe, a rarefaction wave propagates inward from the open end, with each pressure level having its own pressure-propagation wave speed. This characteristic behaviour can be visualized as a decompression curve. When droplet nucleation begins, a plateau or a change in gradient is typically observed in the curve, marking the point where nucleation becomes predominant. Assuming isentropic flow in the pipe, we have calculated the decompression speed using invariants of the Euler equations. Along the isentrope, we have identified both the saturation pressure and the supercooling-limit pressure.

This work presents three new experiments involving full-bore depressurizations of a pipe initially filled with pure CO₂. The initial conditions were chosen to complement eight experiments already reported in the literature. The experiments were conducted with high-speed pressure sampling and multiple pressure sensors near the pipe's open end, enabling precise characterization of the decompression curve. In addition to the pure CO₂ experiments, experiments with nine CO₂-rich mixtures, containing at least 88.9% CO₂, are analysed and compared with model predictions. These mixtures include a range of impurities such as volatile gases (hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, argon and methane) and sulfur dioxide.

The full decompression curves, extending to the choking condition (zero velocity), were plotted for all available experiments using the homogeneous equilibrium model (HEM) and the delayed homogeneous equilibrium model (D-HEM). The mean absolute percentage deviation (MAPD) of the supercooling limit applied in the D-HEM was 3% across all experiments. The saturation pressure applied in the HEM systematically overpredicted the nucleation pressure with an MAPD of 23%, whereas the supercooling-limit predictions appear randomly distributed around the nucleation pressure found in the experiments.

The high accuracy of CNT in predicting nucleation pressure makes D-HEM a valuable tool for evaluating design limits related to the onset of running ductile fractures in pipelines transporting CO₂ in a gas-like state.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Morten Hammer: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization; **Han Deng:** Writing

– review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation; **Anders Austegard:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation; **Svend Tollak Munkejord:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Data availability

The experimental data acquired in this study are available at Zenodo ([Hammer et al., 2025](#)).

Appendix A. Decompression-speed plots of previously published experimental data

In this section, decompression plots are presented for all experiments available in the literature. Except for the experiments of [Munkejord et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Botros et al. \(2017a\)](#), where experimental data were directly available, the decompression speed versus pressure curves were digitally extracted from the source articles. The pure CO₂ experiments are shown first in [Figs. A.1 and A.2](#), while the CO₂-rich mixture experiments are presented in [Figs. A.3 to A.5](#).

(b) Experiment of Maxey (1983).

Fig. A.1. Pure CO₂ decompression speeds (green), compared to HEM (blue) and D-HEM (orange) results. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure is indicated as a red star. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(a) Test 02.

(b) Test 03.

(c) Test 04.

(d) Test 13.

(e) Test 14.

(f) Test 16.

Fig. A.2. Pure CO₂ decompression speeds from Cosham *et al.* (2011) (green), compared to HEM (blue) and D-HEM (orange) results. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure is indicated as a red star. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. A.3. CO₂-mixture decompression speeds from [Cosham et al. \(2011\)](#) (green), compared to HEM (blue) and D-HEM (orange) results. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure is indicated as a red star. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(d) Test 12 (95.7% CO₂, 3.3% H₂, 1.0% SO₂).

Fig. A.4. CO₂-mixture decompression speeds from Cosham et al. (2011) (green), compared to HEM (blue) and D-HEM (orange) results. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure is indicated as a red star. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. A.5. Decompression speed of a 83.3% CO₂, 3.5% N₂, 5.8% O₂, 7.4% Ar mixture by Botros et al. (2017a) (green), compared to HEM (blue) and D-HEM (orange) results. The experimentally derived nucleation pressure indicated as a red star. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

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